

PROBLEMS OF FORMING THE ARTISTIC- AESTHETIC CULTURE OF PRE-SCHOOL CHILDREN THROUGH GAMES

Jumayeva Malika Aliyevna

Teacher of Termiz State Pedagogical Institute

Abstract: In this article, issues such as the formation of the artistic and aesthetic culture of preschool children with the help of game technologies, and the qualitative preparation of them for comprehensive school education were considered.

Key words: game, artistic-aesthetic, MTT, moral standards, self-control ability, incentive and punishment system, interpersonal relations, aesthetic taste, mental and emotional world, dream- expectations, needs.

From preschool age, children begin to guide the process of evaluating their behavior, themselves and other people based on certain moral standards. They develop moral ideas and moral self-control. Close adults and peers who educate children are reflected as a source of moral ideas. Moral experience is passed from adults to children and is acquired in the process of communication, observation and imitation, through a system of incentives and punishments. Communication has a special place in the formation of the personality of a preschool child. We can understand what kind of person a child will grow up to be based on the way a child enters into interpersonal relationships.

Aesthetic education, first of all, has a great influence on the formation of aesthetic tastes of people. A person's identity is manifested through his aesthetic taste. Aesthetic taste expresses the realization of a person's mental and emotional world, hopes, needs, goals and interests. Taste is expressed not only by mood, but also by the results of human activity. His taste is reflected in all the fruits of human activity.

Aesthetic education focuses on the formation of aesthetic needs of a person, unites and harmonizes various complex needs and creates conditions for their harmonious implementation.

The role of aesthetic education in the formation of the culture of human needs is also incomparable, because in the culture of human needs there is a certain sense of criteria, this sense of criteria is to increase personal needs in a proportionate way with the needs of society. requires. Achieving maturity in the sense of this criterion is one of the most important tasks of aesthetic education.

The aesthetic need is not only to enjoy material and spiritual beauty, but also to create things according to the laws of sophistication in any field of practice, and to apply beauty to activities. Therefore, aesthetic education should be applied to all aspects of life - study, work, scientific and technical research, collective activities.

Children of preschool age can often explain their behavior using certain moral categories. This shows that there are signs of moral self-awareness and self-control. True, due to the fact that children of this age pay special attention to the thoughts, views and actions of others, the appearance of the corresponding personal qualities is not stable.

Another peculiarity of the artistic and aesthetic development of older preschool children is related to the changes that occur in the field of cognitive processes. For example, the formation of aesthetic ideals in children is a complex and long-lasting process as a component of worldview. All pedagogues and psychologists have noted this. In the process of upbringing, life relationships and ideals change. Under the influence of friends, adults, works of art, life shocks, ideals can be radically changed. As noted by B. T. Likhachev, "Taking into account age characteristics, in order to form aesthetic ideals in children, it is necessary to create ideal ideas about society, people, and relationships between people in various forms from early childhood. This requires the use of new and interesting forms at every stage.

The educator should take into account the following peculiarities of the artistic and aesthetic development of preschool children:

1) thinking about beauty, the educator should pay attention to the effect of emotions, not the content;

2) connects the artistic-aesthetic feeling with the means of sensory development of art, i.e. the beauty, shape, color, length, lines, and sound of things. For this, it is necessary to organize didactic games for sensory education;

3) because the child is imitative, the educator must give only positive examples.

Taking into account the above, in working with children of preschool educational institutions based on their individual and psychological characteristics, according to the forms of activity that form the main criteria of age characteristics, didactic games, role-playing exercises practical application of lessons serves as a solid basis for the formation of artistic and aesthetic culture in children.

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